

Analytic formulation of the coupling parameter and optical activity in chiral and achiral dimer configurations for arbitrary excitation and scattering directions in three-dimensional space

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For simple nanosystems, it is usually sufficient to investigate the system's behavior under a single polarization excitation. However, in the case of coupled nanoparticles in three-dimensional space, it is often necessary to study different excitation polarizations in different scattering directions and matrix methods using all possible modes of excitation become important. In this note, we examine the optical response of coupled metallic nanorods. We introduce a 3D Jones matrix for arbitrarily oriented nanorods in three-dimensional space and we formulate the scattering matrix of the coupled nanorod system for arbitrary excitation and scattering directions. We also study the optical activity of the nanorod system and show that, contrary to general belief, optical activity does not arise from the coupling (interaction) between nanorods. Although, optical activity for forward scattering occurs only for coupled nanorods, for other scattering directions, in general, the system can manifest strong optical activity even if there is no coupling between the particles. We conclude that the main cause of optical activity is the phase difference in the light rays scattered from different parts of the system.

GENERAL FORMALISM

In the following, we assume that particles can be polarized only along their long axes. Since the system can be rotated as a whole in the three-dimensional space we choose the plane wave excitation in the x - y plane (Fig.1).

FIG. 1. Coupled nanorods in three-dimensional space. \mathbf{k} vectors indicates the direction of wave propagation. Unit vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are the basis of the excitation plane. \mathbf{s} represents the scattering direction. Unit vectors \mathbf{x}' and \mathbf{y}' are the basis of the scattering plane. The sets of vectors \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{y} , \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{x}' , \mathbf{y}' , \mathbf{s} form right-handed orthogonal coordinate systems.

The induced electric dipole moment vector, \mathbf{P} , on a particle is proportional to the incident electric field, $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$:

$$\mathbf{P} = \varepsilon \bar{\bar{\alpha}} \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (1)$$

where ε is the permittivity of the medium at the dipole

position \mathbf{r} . For nanorods in three-dimensional space we define $\bar{\bar{\alpha}}$ as the following rank one matrix:

$$\bar{\bar{\alpha}} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}^T \hat{\mathbf{n}} = \alpha \begin{pmatrix} n_x n_x & n_x n_y & n_x n_z \\ n_y n_x & n_y n_y & n_y n_z \\ n_z n_x & n_z n_y & n_z n_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where α is the scalar Lozentzian polarizability and n_x, n_y, n_z are the components of the unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ that represents the orientation of the nanorod.

When we put two particles close to each other we have to consider mutual interactions. Each one of the induced dipoles experiences the field of the other dipole. This coupling effect should be taken into account to find the actual dipole of the i 'th particle as follows : [1, 2]

$$\mathbf{P}_i = \varepsilon \bar{\bar{\alpha}}_i \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_i) + k^2 \bar{\bar{\alpha}}_i \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N \bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j) \mathbf{P}_j, \quad (3)$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ (N is the number of particles), k is the wavenumber and $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j)$ is the free-space electric dyadic Green's function. The effect of $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j)$ on \mathbf{P}_j is defined as

$$\bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j) \mathbf{P}_j = [A + B \bar{\bar{\mathbf{u}}}] \mathbf{P}_j. \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{u}}} = \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{ij}^T \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{ij}$, $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{ij}$ is the unit position vector between the particles along $\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j$, and

$$A = \left(1 + \frac{i}{kr} - \frac{1}{k^2 r^2} \right) g(r), \quad (5a)$$

$$B = \left(-1 - \frac{3i}{kr} + \frac{3}{k^2 r^2} \right) g(r), \quad (5b)$$

$g(r) = e^{ikr}/4\pi r$ (r is the magnitude of $\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j$).

Eq.(3) generates $3N$ coupled equations to be solved; but they immediately reduce to N coupled equations because $\bar{\bar{\alpha}}$ is of rank one and components of \mathbf{P}_i are proportional to each other. For example, if $n_{ix} \neq 0$:

$$P_{iy} = \frac{n_{iy}}{n_{ix}} P_{ix}, \quad P_{iz} = \frac{n_{iz}}{n_{ix}} P_{ix}, \quad (6)$$

then, we can write Eq.(3) in a simple form only for P_{ix} :

$$P_{ix} = \varepsilon \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_i) + k^2 \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \bar{\bar{\mathbf{G}}}(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j) \mathbf{P}_j, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{v}_i is the first column of $\bar{\bar{\alpha}}_i$.

EXAMPLES

FIG. 2. Coupled nanorods in an achiral configuration.

As an example we consider a rather simple geometry of identical nanorods ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$) given in Fig.2, where we set

$$\mathbf{n}_1 = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) \mathbf{T}; \quad \mathbf{n}_2 = \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) \mathbf{T} \quad (8)$$

Therefore we have

$$P_{1x} = P_{1y} = P_{1z}; \quad P_{2x} = -P_{2y} = -P_{2z} \quad (9)$$

We solve two coupled equations to find P_{1x} and P_{2x} under a plane wave illumination, $\mathbf{E} = (E_x, E_y, 0) \mathbf{T}$:

$$P_{1x} = \frac{\varepsilon \alpha}{3(1 - \delta^2)} [(1 + \delta)E_x + (1 - \delta)E_y] \quad (10)$$

$$P_{2x} = \frac{\varepsilon \alpha}{3(1 - \delta^2)} [(1 + \delta)E_x - (1 - \delta)E_y] \quad (11)$$

where $\delta = \frac{1}{3} k^2 \alpha (3A + B)$. The quadratic form of the denominator suggests two peaks at the spectra of the components of \mathbf{P}_1 and \mathbf{P}_2 that correspond to two hybridized energies [2]. But, when we rearrange the components as a scattering matrix (2D Jones matrix) we get the following:

$$\mathbf{J}_{scat(z)} = \frac{2\varepsilon \alpha}{3} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{1-\delta} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1+\delta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{scat(z)}$ is for scattering in the z -direction. According to the denominators of J_{11} and J_{22} one mode is dark. Resonance of J_{11} shifts to lower energies, whereas resonance of J_{22} shifts to higher energies.

It is worth to note that $\mathbf{J}_{scat(z)}$ is a symmetric matrix, hence the system does not manifest optical activity for forward scattering. We also calculate the scattering matrix for scattering in the x -direction [3]:

$$\mathbf{J}_{scat(x)} = \frac{\varepsilon \alpha}{3} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{e-1}{1-\delta} & -\frac{e+1}{1+\delta} \\ -\frac{e-1}{1-\delta} & \frac{e+1}{1+\delta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where we multiply the components of \mathbf{P}_2 by $e = e^{i2\pi D/\lambda}$, because it is at a distance D behind \mathbf{P}_1 , as viewed from the x -axis, and we make the following transformation of basis for the scattered fields:

$$-z \rightarrow x', \quad y \rightarrow y' \quad (14)$$

and accordingly we let

$$P_{ix'} = -P_{iz}, \quad P_{iy'} = P_{iy}; \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (15)$$

$\mathbf{J}_{scat(x)}$ in Eq.(13) is an asymmetric matrix. The coupled system manifests optical activity for scattering in the x -direction. γ parameter associated with the circular anisotropy of the system is [4]:

$$\gamma_{scat(x)} = \frac{i}{2} (J_{12} - J_{21}) = -\frac{i\varepsilon \alpha (1 - e\delta)}{3(1 - \delta^2)} \quad (16)$$

There is a general belief that emergence of optical activity is due to the coupling between the particles [5–7]. It may be interesting to note that, in this example, $\gamma_{scat(x)} \neq 0$ even if there is no coupling between the particles. No-coupling condition can be satisfied by separating the particles ($\delta \rightarrow 0$):

$$\gamma_{scat(x)}(\delta \rightarrow 0) = -\frac{i\varepsilon \alpha}{3} \quad (17)$$

To clarify this point, we give another example. This time the particles are also separated by the distance d

FIG. 3. Coupled nanorods in a chiral configuration.

along the z -axis (Fig.3). We calculate the Jones matrix for scattering in the z -direction:

$$\mathbf{J}_{scat(z)} = \frac{\varepsilon\alpha}{1-\delta^2} \begin{pmatrix} 2\bar{e} + (1+\bar{e}^2)\delta & (1-\bar{e}^2)\delta \\ -(1-\bar{e}^2)\delta & 2\bar{e} - (1+\bar{e}^2)\delta \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where $\bar{e} = e^{i2\pi d/\lambda}$, $\delta = \frac{1}{3}k^2\alpha(-A + (\bar{u}_{xx} - \bar{u}_{zz})B)$, $\bar{u}_{xx} - \bar{u}_{zz} = \frac{D^2-d^2}{D^2+d^2}$, $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_1) = (E_x, E_y, 0)^T$, $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_2) = (\bar{e}E_x, \bar{e}E_y, 0)^T$. We multiply components of \mathbf{P}_1 by \bar{e} , be-

cause it is at a distance d behind \mathbf{P}_2 , as viewed from the z -axis [8, 9].

$\mathbf{J}_{scat(z)}$ matrix is asymmetric because the phase factor \bar{e} is distributed unevenly over the coupling coefficient δ that appear in the off-diagonal elements. Therefore, the coupled system manifests optical activity for forward scattering (scattering in the z -direction) with the following circular anisotropy parameter:

$$\gamma_{scat(z)} = \frac{i\varepsilon\alpha(1-\bar{e}^2)\delta}{3(1-\delta^2)} \quad (19)$$

However, in this case, $\gamma_{scat(z)}$ directly depends on the interaction coefficient δ , hence as $\delta \rightarrow 0$, $\gamma_{scat(z)} \rightarrow 0$.

When $\delta \rightarrow 0$ the Jones matrix of the system becomes just a sum of individual particle Jones matrices. Jones matrix of a single particle was given elsewhere [10];

$$\mathbf{J}_{single} = \alpha \begin{pmatrix} \eta_x\eta_{x'} & \eta_x\eta_{y'} \\ \eta_y\eta_{x'} & \eta_y\eta_{y'} \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

where η_x, η_y are illumination profiles and $\eta_{x'}, \eta_{y'}$ are scattering profiles. For forward scattering $\eta_x = \eta_{x'}, \eta_y = \eta_{y'}$, hence \mathbf{J}_{single} is a symmetric matrix. This explains why for forward scattering we are always left alone with a symmetric Jones matrix when $\delta \rightarrow 0$.

It is worth to note that even a single nanorod can have an asymmetric Jones matrix for scattering directions other than forward scattering. However, since a single nanorod matrix is a real matrix, the CD (circular dichroism) response of a single particle is always zero, i.e. the response of the particle to RCP and LCP polarization excitation is indistinguishable.

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